

WHAW Quiz

How much do you know about sex differences in health and disease?

1. Of the 880 health joining the WHO in 2005, do you know in what proportion women were represented? (https://apps.who.int/gb/archive/pdf_files/EB116/B116_13-sp.pdf)

- 20%
- 50%
- 80%

2. In Spain, what age range has the biggest gender gap of employment rate?

(https://www.ine.es/ss/Satellite?L=es_ES&c=INESeccion_C&cid=1259925463013&p=1254735110672&pagename=ProductosYServicios%2FPYSLayou¶m1=PYSDetalle¶m3=1259924822888)

- 16 to 24
- 25 to 54
- 55 to 64

3. Who have higher healthy life years at birth in percentage of the total life expectancy?

(https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dqs/indicator/bpfa_c_offic_c1_bpfa_c1b)

- Women
- Men
- Comparable survival rate.

4. Who are more likely to develop chronic pain* in their lifetime? (* long standing pain that persists beyond the usual recovery period or occurs along with chronic health conditions)

([Book:Unwell Women. Elinor Cleghorn](#))

- Women
- Men

5. In Europe, Cardiovascular Disease constitutes 36% of all mortality among men (900,000 deaths) and 44% among women (1 million deaths). Which of these symptoms are more frequent in women than in men for heart attacks?

(<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/8c207181-b7ac-46b8-8e63-f418cc39e53c/language-en>)

- Back pain
- Shortness of breath
- Pain in the chest
- Cold sweat and nausea
- Unusual fatigue

6. Who survives less frequently to an acute coronary event?

https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dgs/indicator/bpfa_c_offic_c3_bpfa_c3hist

- Women
- Men
- Comparable survival rate.

7. Do you think that the sex or gender of a person influences the risk of contracting infectious diseases? Do you know what the proportion of men and women infected by COVID-19 has been worldwide?. <https://youtu.be/2-F35SF-6ws>

- Same
- More men than women
- More women than men

8. In how many medicines out of the 10 medicines withdrawn from the market due to side effects were such effects produced mainly in women? <https://youtu.be/S7whF15jlfE>

- 2 out of 10
- 8 out of 10
- There is not difference between men and women

9. Medications affect men and women differently. Which of the following factors are responsible for these differences? <https://www.aafp.org/afp/2009/1201/p1254.html>

- Body mass index
- Intestinal enzymatic activity
- Renal clearance
- All of the above are correct

10. Men's depression and other mental health problems are under-detected and under treated in all European countries. This is partly due to men's difficulty in seeking help, and health services' limited capacity to reach out to men. Would you know which of these symptoms correspond to depression in men?

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/8c207181-b7ac-46b8-8e63-f418cc39e53c/language-en>

- Lack of interest
- Sadness
- Substance Abuse
- Risk behaviors
- Apathy
- Antisocial Disorders

11. Which of these are the correct proportions of men and women to suffer depression in elderly populations?

<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s001270050043>

- 19.6% men and 46% women
- 5.2% men and 24.4% women
- 43.8% men and 36.2% women
- 28.9.% men and 7.8% women

12. Several studies have suggested a key role of the gut microbiome in the development of inflammatory bowel diseases (IBD). These are more prevalent in females than males. The gut microbiome associated to IBD is influenced by:

Link: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0154090>

- Gender
- Body Mass Index (BMI)
- Both Gender and BMI